

Determination of Heavy Metal Contents in the Medicinal Plant *Mentha longifolia* Collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley, District Quetta, Balochistan

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants are used as herbal formulations in the rural areas. *Mentha longifolia* is the member of mentheae and it belongs to the genus *Mentha*. It is widely used since ancient times to treat a variety of diseases and distributed in Pakistan, India, Syria, Iran, Iraq and Egypt. The plants have been widely used as a biological monitor because of the ability to absorb and assimilate the inorganic nutrients from surroundings and accumulate them in the leaves of the plant. The plant samples were analyzed for the determination of metals including (Cd), cobalt (Co), Copper (Cu), Iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), Nickel (Ni), and Lead (Pb) using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS). The results revealed that Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, and Pb showed the lower concentration 0.175, 0.1836, 0.4525, 14.2635, 0.5367, 0.3045, 2.570 ppm respectively in plant collected from Aghbarg whereas the sample collected from Hanna Valley showed the higher concentration of Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni and Pb which were 0.2215, 0.1987, 0.5735, 17.5246, 0.6814, 0.4108, 3.0564 ppm. The observed concentrations of heavy metals were lower as compared to WHO / FAO permissible limits. The present study aimed to determine the heavy metal contamination in medicinal plant *Mentha longifolia*. The findings provide information on heavy metal related risks helping local communities to take measures to protect human health and environment.

1. Introduction

Medicinal plants are widely used as a raw material for many herbal remedies. There is a widely held belief that herbal medicines have no adverse effects and are safe due to their natural occurrence, this assumption is not always true. The absorption of heavy metals in plants is obvious due to widespread and extensive heavy metals found in the soil due to meteorological conditions (Jena et al., 2007). These heavy metals have high tendency to accumulate in human organs and causes metabolic disorders due to excess accumulation of zinc, copper, and cadmium which are essential micronutrients in our body and can produce toxic effects and cause serious health complications (Witkowska, et al., 2021). WHO has recommended monitoring of heavy metals in medicinal plants because raw material of these plants used in the preparations of the herbal supplements and pharmaceutical products (Subramanian et al., 2012).

Mentha longifolia is the member of family *Mentheae* and genus *Mentha*. It is a wild mint and also known as horse mint. It comprises about 25–30 species, have simple leaves with five sepals and petals, white or purple color flower. The leaves are narrow at the tip and broader in middle. These plants are found in terrestrial and wetlands, especially at seashores and near rivers. The growing season of *Mentha longifolia* is from spring to winter because its seed germination requires the temperature range 18 to 25°C and requires fine light for germination. The flowering occurs in late spring or summer but in subtropical regions like Mediterranean regions growth start in late winter and run into autumn but still flowering occur in summer. *Mentha longifolia* distributed all over the world, especially in the Mediterranean region, Australia, and Africa (Dorman et al., 2003). *M. longifolia* has been used in many medicines to cure a variety of diseases like inflammatory, infectious, respiratory and intestinal problems. The variety of activities has been reported such as antiseptic and antimicrobial activities. *Mentha longifolia* widely used in ancient time to cure a variety of diseases and widely distributed in Srilanka, Pakistan, India, Syria, Iran, Iraq, Egypt (Rajurkar et al., 1992).

Due to excessive anthropogenic activities, heavy metal contamination has been a source of attention which increases inorganic pollution. Many plants have been used as a biological monitor owing tendency to absorb and assimilate the inorganic nutrients from surroundings and accumulate in the leaves of the plant. Plants accumulate between 1,000 mg/kg and 10,000 mg/kg of specific metals are categorized as hyper-accumulators. The variety of plants absorbs these micronutrients from soil with help of their roots (Baker, 1989). The present study aims to provide valuable insights into the extent and nature of heavy metal contamination in medicinal plant *Mentha longifolia* in Quetta district, Balochistan. The

findings have provided information for policymakers, public health officials, and local communities about the potential risks for the presence of heavy metals in medicinal plants to protect public health and the environment.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection of Plant

The plant samples were collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley, District Quetta, Balochistan. Taxonomic identification of the plant was carried out by Dr. Shazia Saeed, Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, University of Balochistan, Quetta.

2.2. Washing and Drying

The collected plant samples were washed with deionized water to remove surface contaminants and impurities. Subsequently, the samples were cut into small pieces of approximately uniform size and placed in clean crucibles. The samples were then oven-dried at 50 °C until a constant dry and brittle state was achieved.

2.3. Grinding/ Sample Size Reduction

The dried plant material was homogenized by grinding it into a fine powder using a mortar and pestle. The resulting powdered samples were subsequently transferred into polyethylene bags and stored for further analytical processing.

2.4. Digestion of the Samples

One gram of each plant sample was accurately weighed into a 50 mL beaker. Subsequently, 10 mL of concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) was added, and the mixture was placed on a hot plate for 20–25 minutes to facilitate oxidation. After heating, the beaker was removed from the hot plate and allowed to cool. Thereafter, 5 mL of perchloric acid (HClO₄) was added, and the mixture was reheated until the appearance of white fumes. The digested sample was then removed and cooled. Finally, the solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42 and diluted to a final volume of 50 mL with deionized water. The prepared samples were analyzed using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS).

2.5. Analysis of the Samples

The samples were analyzed for the determination of metals including Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, and Pb using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) at the Department of Biochemistry, University of Balochistan, Quetta.

3. Result and Discussion

The AAS analysis revealed that all heavy metals were found in the samples of *Mentha longifolia*. The results obtained for heavy metals such as Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni and Pb are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Concentration of Heavy Metals in *Mentha longifolia* Collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley Areas (ppm)

Metals	Samples	
	Aghbarg	Hanna Valley
Cd	0.175	0.2215
Co	0.1836	0.1987
Cu	0.4525	0.5735
Fe	14.2635	17.5246
Mn	0.5367	0.6814
Ni	0.3045	0.4108
Pb	2.570	3.0564

Cadmium (Cd)

Cadmium is a trace element and it is very toxic for human health. At higher concentrations, it can cause several diseases such as diarrhea, vomiting and abdominal problems. Due to acid rain and agricultural waste, its concentration can increase and may contaminate the soil. Cadmium may be absorbed by the root system in the plants (Hakeem, 2020). The findings revealed that cadmium showed the lower concentration (0.175 ppm) in plant collected from Aghbarg whereas the sample collected from Hanna Valley showed the higher concentration (0.2215 ppm). The detected cadmium concentration was lower than the permissible limits reported by WHO / FAO. The results are displayed in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Concentration of Cadmium in samples collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley

Cobalt (Co)

Cobalt is an essential element that plays an important role in the formation of vitamin B12 and the production of red blood cells. The excess and deficiency of the cobalt can cause health problems. Deficiency of cobalt can cause anemia, whereas the excess can cause serious problems such as heart failure and digestive issues in human body (Elbagermi et al., 2012). The results concluded that cobalt was present in lower concentration (0.1836 ppm) in the samples which were collected from Aghbarg whereas higher concentration (0.1987 ppm) was detected in the plant samples collected from Hanna Valley. The observed concentrations of cobalt were lower as compared to WHO / FAO permissible limits. The results are displayed in the figure 2.

Figure 2: Concentration of Cobalt in samples collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley

Copper (Cu)

Copper is vital element for the human body, as it helps to supply energy to body cells and plays role in oxidative reactions through enzymes. It also participates in the estrogen metabolism, which plays role in female fertility and pregnancy maintenance. A lack of copper can cause central nervous system disorders, thyroid dysfunction and hair related issues. At high concentration, copper acts as a toxin, it can lead to reduced hemoglobin levels and decrease erythrocyte counts. It can also develop cancer in humans (Hakeem et al., 2020). The AAS analysis confirmed the lower concentration of copper (0.4525 ppm) which was collected from Aghbarg whereas the sample collected from Hanna Valley was present in higher concentration (0.5735 ppm). The concentration of copper was lower as compared to the WHO / FAO permissible limits. The results are displayed in the figure 3.

Figure 3: Concentration of Copper in samples collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley

Iron (Fe)

Iron is an important trace element that plays an essential role in the health of living organisms. The lesser amount of iron is required for the body cells to perform physiological functions in human body. Iron is the vital component of hemoglobin in red blood cells and transports oxygen to the tissues of the body. The deficiency and excess of iron can harm the human body. The low concentrations of iron can cause anemia whereas the excess can lead to heart diseases and liver cancer. The high concentration of the iron also interferes in the deposition of zinc in the body (Habib et al., 2012). The analysis results revealed that iron was present in lower concentration (14.2635 ppm) in the sample collected from Aghbarg as compared to the sample collected from Hanna Valley was present in higher concentration (17.5246 ppm). The concentration of iron was lower in both samples according to WHO / FAO permissible limits. The results are displayed in the figure 4.

Figure 4: Concentration of Iron in samples collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley

Manganese (Mn)

Manganese is a trace metal that acts as an antioxidant and plays a vital role in the metabolism of proteins, carbohydrates and cholesterol. The manganese can be stored in the liver, bones and kidneys (Hellen et al., 2014). Manganese was analyzed by using AAS. It confirmed the lower concentration (0.5367 ppm) in the plant samples collected from Aghbarg and higher concentration (0.6814 ppm) in the Hanna Valley samples. The concentration of Manganese was in accordance with WHO /FAO allowed limits. The results are displayed in the figure 5.

Figure 5: Concentration of Manganese in samples collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley
Nickel (Ni)

Nickel is a trace metal present in various enzymes of plants, microbes and humans. It has essential role in the biological processes such as catalyst in the intestinal absorption of iron. It also affects the immune system whereas the excess presence of nickel can results in weight loss, liver damage and increased heart rate (Nisa et al., 2020). The AAS analysis revealed the lower concentration (0.3045 ppm) of plant sample collected from Aghbarg and higher concentration (0.4108 ppm) from the Hanna Valley sample. The concentrations of nickel were lower as compared to WHO / FAO permissible limits. The results are displayed in the figure 6.

Figure 6: Concentration of Nickel in samples collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley
Lead (Pb)

Lead is very toxic metal, it can even harm at low concentrations. Its presence causes serious risks to the environmental and public health. Lead can lead to damage central nervous system. It can also affect sperm quality in men to reduce fertility. It also causes increased birth defects and miscarriages in women (Hellen et al., 2014). Lead was analyzed by using AAS and it showed lower concentration (2.570 ppm) in the plant sample collected from Aghbarg whereas the sample collected from Hanna Valley was present in the higher concentration (3.0564 ppm). The lead was present in lower concentration according to WHO / FAO permissible limits. The results are displayed in the figure 7.

Figure 7: Concentration of Lead in samples collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley

4. Conclusion

The plants have been used as herbal formulations in the local communities and rural areas. It has been observed that they contain contaminants which can be added to plant through soil or water contamination. This study was designed to determine the concentration of heavy metals in the *Mentha longifolia*, which is an important medicinal plant and it has been used against many diseases by the people. This study was particularly focused on the plant which was collected from Aghbarg and Hanna Valley, Quetta district, Balochistan. The results have revealed that the plant which was collected from Aghbarg has showed the lower concentrations of heavy metals whereas the plant collected from Hanna Valley has showed the higher concentrations of heavy metals. The overall concentrations were lesser as compared to the permissible limits of the WHO / FAO. The study concluded that it provided a new information about the presence of heavy metals in the medicinal plant *Mentha longifolia*. This information will also help the local communities about the presence of toxic metals in the commonly used plant.

5. References

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